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OBSERVATIONS ON HANUMANNĀṬAKA

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Though mostly an anthology, the *Hanumannāṭaka* represents a version of the Rāma-story with some telling innovations that combine to invest it with a distinct personality.

Though designated as such and divided into Acts marked by a sprinkling of prose passages and sundry stage-directions, the *Hanumannāṭaka* (*HN*)¹ is an apology for a drama. The two recensions consisting respectively of nine acts with 791 verses and fourteen acts comprised of 579 stanzas, in which the *HN* is currently available bear testimony to the measure of popularity it has enjoyed, over the years. With the bulk of verses bodily lifted from the earlier Rāma-plays, especially the *Prasannarāghava* (*PR*) and the *Anargharāghava* (*AR*), it essentially boils down to a compendium of the *Rāmāyana*. However, the substantial divergences it displays from Vālmiki's text entitle it to be broadly rated as a sort of independent version of the epic story. The variations in the *core* episodes and crucial events may not be many in number, it is their peculiarity and significance in the story that form the rationale of the play and merit a searching appraisal.

Act One commands a broad spectrum. Preliminaries apart, it encompasses in the body of mere fifty-four verses the epic story from Rāma's birth to his return to Ayodhya after his marriage at Mithilā. It is, however, his lively encounter with Paraśurāma, furious at his

1. Ed. Manna Lal Abhimanyu, Chaukhamba Vidya Bhavan, Varanasi, 1992.

audacity in snapping the blow of his mentor, Lord Śiva, that forms the life-breath of the Act and invests it with pleasing freshness. While in Vālmīki's epic the bout purports to be a sort of interception of Rāma's entourage in the course of his journey back home by the enraged sage, with his vaunt evaporating in thin air the moment the prince draws with equal ease the bow of Viṣṇu as well;² in the *HN*. the encounter precedes the solemnization of the royal marriage and degenerates notwithstanding the restraint exercised by Rāma into a game of invectives with the impetuous Lakṣmaṇa as an over active participant adding fuel to the fire with undue frequency. The author of the *HN*. might have been indebted for the episode, to the *PR*. and the *Bhusuṇḍi Rāmāyaṇa* (BR.). It seems to have cast its spell on Goswāmī Tulasīdāsa, the celebrated author of the *Rāmacaritamānasa* (*RCM*) and forms one of the sources of the sage's encounter with the two brothers as brilliantly detailed by him in his epic. Tulasīdāsa seems to have been so enamoured of the heady episode that he has not only adapted some of the parallel verses in the *HN*. , he has also not hesitated in picking up quite a few phrases and words from the original. Some of the borrowals and adaptations merit notice.

In the *HN*., Sītā seeks to draw a contrast between the tender form of Rāma, for whom she has taken fancy by now and the mighty bow, and further expresses her dismay at her father's wisdom in prescribing it as a precondition of her marriage. She is evidently apprehensive of Rāma's capacity to deal with the bow.

कमठकठोरमिदं धनुर्मधुरमूर्तिरसौ रघुनन्दनः ।

कथमधिज्यमनेन विधीयतामहह तात पणस्तव दारुणः ॥

HN. I. 10.

The verse has been neatly absorbed by Tulasīdāsa in the body of

2. *Rāmāyaṇa*, Gita Press, I. 74, 75, 76. 1-15.

three lines that follow, though the sequence of the contrast and Sītā's dismay has been reversed here. Far from impairing the effect of the original, the explicit expression in the *Rāmacaritamānasa* serves to heighten the poetic impact and beauty.

नीकें निरखि नयन भरि सोभा। पितु पनु सुमिरि बहुरि मन छोभा।।
 अहह तात दारुन हठ ठानी। समुझतु नहिं कष्टु लाभ न हानी।।
 कहें धनु कुलिसहु चाहि कठोरा। कहें स्यामल मृदु गात किसोरा।।³

While पितु पनु सुमिरि बहुरि मन छोभा is but an echo of अहह तात पणस्तव दारुणः, the second line is intended to be a commentary of sorts on the crisp expression. It is addedly marked by verbal borrowing from the original. The words अहह तात दारुन have obviously been lifted from the verse. By comparing the bow with the thunderbolt in preference to the Kamaṭha, the third line means to highlight the unassailability of the bow and thereby conveys the contrast more emphatically.

Responding with alacrity to Rāma's expression of surprise at the failure of the vast array of suitors in lifting or bending the bow, which conjures up to him of the vision of the earth void of powerful men (*HN*. I.11), Lakṣmaṇa offers, if permitted by him, to successfully deal with the bow.

देव श्रीरघुनाथ किं बहुतया, दासोऽस्मि ते लक्ष्मणो
 मेर्वादीनपि भूधरान्न गणये, जीर्णः पिनाकः कियान्।
 तन्मामादिश पश्य पश्य च बलं भृत्यस्य यत्कौतुकं
 प्रोद्धर्तुं प्रतिनामितुं प्रचलितुं नेतुं निहन्तुं क्षमः।।

HN., I.12

Tulasīdāsa has adapted the verse in the following excerpt with a

3. *Śrī Rāmacaritamānasa* (Medium size), Gita Press, 14th edition, p.246.

substantially improved expression which transforms it into a more poetic and forceful piece.

जौ तुम्हारि अनुसासन पावौं। कंदुक इव ब्रह्मांड उठावौं॥
 काचे घट जिमि डारौं फोरी। सकउं मेरु मूलक जिमि तोरी॥
 तव प्रताप महिमा भगवाना। को बापुरो पिनाक पुराना॥
 नाथ जानि अस आयसु होउ। कौतुक करौं विलोकिअ सोऊ॥
 कमल नाल जिमि चाप चढावौं। जोजन सत प्रमान लै धावौं॥⁴

Compared with Tulasīdāsa's piece, the original sounds prosaic. The expression of Lakṣmaṇa's prowess in मेवादीनपि भूधरान्न गणये is rather casual and insipid. Tulasī has not only revealed what was latent in *ādīnapi*, he has by comparing Brahmāṇḍa with Kanduka and Meru with Mūlaka (raddish) effectively underscored the unbounded strength and self-confidence of Lakṣmaṇa. To say that he would toss the universe like a small ball and crush it down like an unbaked pitcher, and break the Meru with effortless ease like a raddish is certainly more poetic. जीर्णः पिनाकः कियान् in the original is paralleled by 'को बापुरो पिनाक पुराना in the *RCM* which, besides being a verbal translation of its prototype, seeks to belittle the mighty bow more effectively. And by crediting the prospective feat to Lord Rāma, Tulasīdāsa has addedly brought home Lakṣmaṇa's modesty, his provocative and mischevious retorts to Paraśurāma in his epic notwithstanding. The third line of the verse "तन्मामादिश पश्य पश्य च बलं भृत्यस्य यत्कौतुकम्" is virtually paraphrased as नाथ जानि अस आयसु होउ। कौतुक करौं विलोकिअ सोऊ॥ Needless to say that आयसु होउ and कौतुक करौं विलोकिअ सोऊ respectively correspond to तन्मामादिश and पश्य पश्य च बलं भृत्यस्य यत् कौतुकम्. While the fourth line of the verse etc. is pedestrian, Tulasīdāsa has turned it into a more polished and impressive expression that again serves to highlight the young prince

4. *Ibid.*, p. 242.

(Lakṣmaṇa's) funds of physical and spiritual prowess. कमल नाल जिमि चाप चढ़ावौं। जोजन सत प्रमान लै धावौं overshadows its original both in crispness and poetic beauty.

With Rāvaṇa reluctant to trife with the bow of his mentor and other suitors unable to do so, Janaka pities the lot of his daughter in the following verse.

माहेश्वरो दशग्रीवः क्षुद्राश्चान्ये महीभुजः।

पिनाकारोपणं शुल्कं हा सीते किं भविष्यति।।

HN. I.17.

Tulasīdāsa has assimilated the idea in his own way in a couplet which, not unlike the earlier adaptations, bespeaks his poetic talents in giving the original a more winsome garb.

अब जनि कोउ भाखै भट मानी। वीर विहीन मही मैं जानी।

तजहु आस निज निज गृह जाहू। लिखा न विधि वैदेहि विवाहू।।⁵

Though modelled on क्षुद्राश्चान्ये महीभुजः Tulasī's expression वीरविहीन मही मैं जानी brings out the helplessness of the suitors in the situations more effectively. हा सीते किं भविष्यति is doubtless more suggestive. By rendering it as लिखा न विधि वैदेहि विवाहू Tulasīdāsa has made it more explicit. And तजहु आस निज निज गृह जाहू is a manifestation of Janaka's abhorrence of the haughty rulers who had flocked to try their luck with the bow.

The description of the sound of the Pināka, when snapped by Rāma, has been a favourite theme with the Sanskrit playwrights. Not unoften, they break into hyperbole and prolixity. As detailed by the author of the *HN.*, it is alleged to have set the universe into commotion, shaking the earth to its moorings and causing even the sun to deflect from its course.

⁵. *ibid.* p. 241.

त्रुटयद्भीमधनुः कठोरनिनदस्तत्राकरोद्विस्मयं
 त्रस्यदवाजिरवेरमार्गगमनं शम्भोः शिरःकम्पनम्।
 दिग्दन्तिस्खलनं कुलाद्रिचलनं सप्तार्णवोन्मेलनं
 वैदेहीमदनं मदान्धदमनं त्रैलोक्यसम्मोहनम्॥

HN., I.27

Tulasīdāsa has recast the verse in his mould, though that does not conceal his indebtedness to the *H.N.* He has doubtless replaced *Śambhoḥ śiraḥkampanam, kulādricalanam* etc. by the omnibus phrase अहि कोल कूरुम कलमले, but besides picking up the word *kaṭhōra* from the play, he has, not unlike it, pointedly described the swerving of the sun from its normal path as one of the consequences of the terrific sound.

तेहि छन राम मध्य धनु तोरा। भरे भुवन धुनि घोर कठोरा।
 भरे भुवन घोर कठोर रव बाजि तजि मारगु चले।
 चिक्करहिं दिग्गज डोल महि अहि कोल कूरुम कलमले॥⁶

Paraśurāma's sudden emergence on the scene has prompted the playwright to draw a vibrant pen-sketch of the furious sage. His eternal celibacy, chopping down the thousand arms of Kārttavīrya and his clearing the earth of the Kṣatriya race, times without number, and its consequent gifting to the Brāhmaṇas have been sought to be detailed in three consecutive verses in the *HN.* (I. 32-34). Tulasīdāsa has drawn upon them to give an integrated picture of the sage, enraged at the slight.

बाल ब्रम्हचारी अति कोही। बिस्व विदित छत्रिय कुल द्रोही॥
 भुजबल भूमि भूप बिनु कीन्ही। विपुल बार महिदेवन्ह दीन्ही॥
 सहसबाहु भुज छेदन हारा। परसु बिलोकु महीप कुमारा॥⁷

6. *Ibid.* p. 249.

7. *Ibid.*, p. 257.

Here बाल ब्रह्मचारी doubtless corresponds to आजन्म ब्रह्मचारी (I.32). बिस्व विदित छत्रिय कुल द्रोही and भुजबल भूमि-दीन्ही form an adaptation of राजन्यगोष्ठीवनगजमृगयाकौतुकी (I.32) and येन त्रिसप्त कृत्वो etc. (I.34). What is described at length in I. 33 finds echo in सहसबाहु भुज छेदनहारा। परसु बिलोकु महीपकुमारा।।

Despite persistent provocations and threats from Paraśurāma, Rāma does not lose his cool. He rather begs his pardon for the 'lapse'.⁸ He tells Paraśurāma in unmistakable terms that whatever the odds, we of the Raghu race never take up arms against the *Brāhmaṇas* and the cows.

निहन्तुं हन्त गोविप्रान्न शूरा रघुवंशजाः। HN. I.40

Tulasīdāsa was so overwhelmed by the high idealism revealed in the hemistich that he thought it best to merely paraphrase it, adding gods and Harijanas to the list.

सुर महिसुर हरिजन अरु गाई। हमरें कुल इन्ह पर न सुराई।⁹

Rāma goes to the extent of sticking out his neck to Paraśurāma to do with it as he pleased. अयं कण्ठः कुठारस्ते कुरु राम यथोचितम् (HN., I. 40). Tulasīdāsa was deeply touched by Rāma's modesty and reverential behaviour with the sage. He has seized upon the pithy sentence to expand it at some length in his epic.

अपराधी में नाथ तुम्हारा।

कृपा कोपु बहु बंधव गोसाई। मों पर करिअ दास की नाई।¹⁰

करु कुठार आगे यह सीसा।¹¹

When Paraśurāma had the audacity to test Rāma's might by inviting him to draw Viṣṇu's bow to prove that the earlier feat was no

8. तच्चापलं परशुराम मम क्षमस्व। HN. I.39

9. *Rāmacaritamānasa*, op. cit. p. 258.

10. *Ibid.* p. 262.

11. *Ibid.* p. 264.

fluke, the prince did that with incredible ease. That filled the sage with wonder and left him aghast. This is how the author of the *HN*. has described the event.

राजन्यकप्रधनसाधनमस्मदीयमाकर्ष कार्मुकमिदं गरुडध्वजस्य ॥ *HN*. I. 46

रामस्तदादाय धनुः सहेलं बाणं गुणे योज्य यदाचकर्ष ।

भाति स्म साक्षान्मकरध्वजः स्वर्गतिं प्रचिच्छेद च भार्गवस्य ॥ *HN*., I.50.

Tulasidāsa has drawn upon the verses and has summed them up in mere two lines.

राम रमापति कर धनु लेह । खँचहु चाप मिटै सन्देह ॥

देत चाप आपहि चलि गयऊ । परसुराम मन विसमय भयऊ ॥¹²

Some other stanzas, as found in the *HN*., also form the source of quite a few pieces in the *RCM*., but since they have been borrowed from other plays it would be better to leave them out of consideration.

The second Act breaks into a daring departure from the epic story and sets at naught the high moral values it seeks to uphold. In it are described with abandon the sexual sports of Rāma and Sītā which cannot but remind one of the similar amourettes detailed in the eighth canto of the *Kumārasāmbhava*. The description perhaps owes itself to the *Bhusuṇḍi-Rāmāyaṇa* (*BR*.), which, obviously under the impact of the various Tantric systems and the Rasika strand of the Viṣṇu cult, is padded with sizable erotic sports of the divine couple. Howsoever shocking and repulsive, the sexual orgy of Rāma and Sītā, had become an inalienable trapping of the cult. As a representative text of the system, it was natural for the *BR*. to address itself to these amourettes with a measure of tenacity.

12. *Ibid.* p. 266.

However, the description in the *HN* betrays substantial divergences from the *BR.*, both in contents and approach to the affair. In the *BR.* Sītā is portrayed as a coy girl, averse to the advances made by the hero to win her over. She stoutly resists attempts to temper with her girdle and the lower garment.¹³ She does not hesitate in separating him with a well-aimed kick.¹⁴ Even when her gimmicks such as the concealing of the privy part¹⁵ and feigning sleep¹⁶ are foiled and she is cornered with no alternative left to her, she timidly appeals to Rāma to proceed gently in the affair.¹⁷ But that does not deter him from the violent game which leaves red even the bed.¹⁸

As depicted in the *HN*, however, Sītā represents the other pole. She appears to be a willing partner in the act. With moonshine forming the captivating backdrop, she readily proceeds to the *boudoir*, imparting immense pleasure to Rāma,¹⁹ who in excitement carries her to the bed.²⁰ She feels no qualms in giving expression to her welling emotions.²¹ Feeble resistance apart, she carries out the act with gusto, exchanging kisses and caresses, which combine to turn the world into a blessed haven of pleasure and enjoyment for them.²² In enclosing Rāma into a tight embrace and subsequently

13. बलेन सा तस्य सुबाहुयन्त्रणां निवार्य नीवीं प्रददौ करं हि सा। *Bhuṣuṇḍi-Rāmāyaṇa* (*BR.*). Vishvavidyalaya Prakashan, Varanasi, 1975 A.D., I. 28.31.
14. हठात् समाकृष्य पदद्वयेन सा विव्याथ वक्षःस्थलमस्य कामिनः।। *Ibid.* I. 28.36.
15. पिधाय योनिं करपद्मसम्पुटे—*Ibid.* I. 28.47
16. पराङ्मुखी तावदभूज्जवेन सा। *Ibid.* I. 28.49
17. अलं जवेन प्रिय मुञ्च मुञ्च मां—*Ibid.* I. 28.52
18. स भाष्यमाणोऽपि जवेन योनिं बभञ्ज तस्याः खलु दीनयाचितम्। *Ibid.* I.28.53—ररञ्ज शय्यापि यथार्द्रयावकैः। *Ibid.* I. 28.54
19. *HN.* II.2
20. *Ibid.*, II.10
21. बाणान्पञ्च प्रवदति जनः पञ्चबाणोऽप्रमाणै—
र्बाणैः किं मां प्रहरति शनैर्व्याहरन्ती जगाम।। *Ibid.*, II.10
22. *Ibid.* II. 12

loosening the grip to afford him a modicum of respite, Sītā in the *HN*. has the trappings of a *Praudhā*.²³ The trappings unfold themselves in a variety of amorous actions, which certainly do not emanate from a newly wed maiden.²⁴ Even when exhausted with the nocturnal orgy, she has the temerity to offer the hero her *rasanā* with a provocative invitation to enjoy it.²⁵

Act Three is also characterised by notable deviations from the known epic story. According to the version recorded in the play, Rāma is not banished due to a harem-intrigue. It is to pacify the evil portents that had been haunting the royal palace ever since the arrival of Sītā in the family, that Kaikeyī demands Rāma's exile and throne for her son Bharata.²⁶ A hint to the so-called boons (*vāgbandha*) is made but it is too subdued to merit serious attention. The *HN* is perhaps the sole text to attribute such a devastating act as Rāma's exile to an irrational belief in frivolities. The playwright seems to be soft to Kaikeyī who, though labelled as *kulāṅgāramūrtiḥ* is spared the harsh denunciation she is subjected to by Bharata in the epic.²⁷

The sequence of events in the Act is grossly distorted, rather thrown overboard. Contrary to the epic version, Bharata is said to have been present at Ayodhyā when his mother asked Daśaratha to meet her whimsical demand. And the old king dies²⁸ before Rāma could leave for the forest.²⁹

23. *Ibid.* II. 11

24. पृथुलजघनभारं मन्दमान्दोलयन्ती, मृदुचलदलकाग्रा प्रस्फुरत्कर्णपूरा ।
प्रकटितभुजमूला दर्शितस्तन्यलीला प्रमदयति पतिं द्राग्जानकी व्याजनिद्रा ॥ *Ibid.* II. 17.

25. पिब पिब रसनां मे कामतो निर्विशङ्कम् । *Ibid.*, II. 21

26. *Ibid.*, Prose Passage, p. 37, कैकेयी वाचमूचे निखिलनिजकुलाङ्गारमूर्तिः ससीतः/
शान्त्यै पुत्रस्य राज्यं भवतु, वनमभिप्रेष्यतामेष रामः// *Ibid.* III. 37

27. *Rāmāyaṇa*, op. cit. II. 73, 74.

28. निश्वस्य दीर्घतरमुच्छ्वसितं न भूयः । *HN*. III:7

29. *Ibid.*, III. 9-11.

The most astounding variation is found in the episode of the *svaṇnamṛga*. According to the version of the play Rāma goes to hunt down the mysterious deer, alongwith Lakṣmaṇa who, before leaving, draws a line with the tip of his bow in front of the cottage to ward off any mishap in their absence.³⁰ In the Tibetan version of the Rāma-story, Lakṣmaṇa is said to have raised a fence around the cottage, and asked Sītā not to go beyond it. On Sītā's refusal to move from the enclosure, Rāvaṇa carries her off together with the whole plot of land.³¹ The *HN* is indeed the solitary text to make the two brothers chase the deer simultaneously, leaving behind Sītā, obviously to her fate.

While in most of the Indian texts including the *HN* (III. 24), the demon Mārīca assumes the form of a golden deer to dupe Rāma, as bidden by his master, in the Tibetan account it is Rāvaṇa's sister who transforms herself into a deer to settle scores with the prince.³² The Malayan version substitutes two gazelles³³ for the one, known from the vast majority of sources.

The famous verse ग्रीवामङ्गामिरामं etc. borrowed from the *Śākuntalam*, has no *locus standi* in the play as there is no chariot chasing the deer. The verse seems to have been inducted in the play because of the author's fascination for it.

The killing of Vālin by Rāma as a part of his pact with Sugrīva has been a highly debatable subject, down the ages. In the *Rāmāyaṇa*, Vālin severely upbraids Rāma for his recklessness and

30. *Ibid.*, III. 27

31. J.W. De Jong : "The story of Rāma in Tibet", in *Asian Variations in Rāmāyaṇa* (ed. K.R. Srinivasa Iyengar), Sahitya Akademi, New Delhi, 1983, p.170.

32. *Asian Variations in Rāmāyaṇa*, op. cit. p. 178.

33. *Ibid.*, p. 285.

seeks to convince him of his innocence in unmistakable terms.³⁴ It is ironic that in the *HN*, Rāma himself comes to entertain doubt about the validity of his action. He is rather convinced of Vālin's innocence and suffers from remorse for having killed him without any cogent reason.³⁵ It is interesting that Rāma showers fulsome praise on Vālin for having avenged his father's (Indra's) defeat at Meghanāda's hands by subjecting Rāvaṇa to abject humiliation (V. 55). Vālin, on the other hand, pours scorn on him, reminding him that what Sugrīva is supposed to do for him, he could have done it better (V. 56).³⁶

Bhavabhūti, a sensitive poet as he was, felt outraged at Rāma's liquidating Vālin apparently for no valid reason. He has sought to correct the aberration by making Vālin undertake an expedition against Rāma. He is killed in the encounter that ensues. He regrets the venture undertaken at the instance of his friend Rāvaṇa³⁷ The change is evidently intended to absolve Rāma of the stigma of killing an innocent person.

The distinguishing mark used by Sugrīva in his combat with Vālin is faintly hinted at in the *HN* (VIII. 13). It doubtless accords with the epic, but while in the *Rāmāyaṇa*, Sugrīva is invested, with a garland of Gajapuṣpī flowers,³⁸ the mark is mysteriously left unspecified in the play. He is found in some alien versions resorting to funny things like mirror and shell to distinguish himself from his combatant brother.³⁹ Interestingly, there is no trace of enmity between them in Bhavabhūti's

34. हत्वा बाणेन काकुत्स्थ मामिहानपराधिनम् । किं वक्ष्यसि सतां मध्ये कर्म कृत्वा जुगुप्सितम् ॥
Rāmāyaṇa, IV. 17.35
35. अनपराधिनं बालिनं हत्वा मन्दभाग्यः कथमहं जानकीसुखमनुभविष्यामीति । *HN*.p. 77
36. Compare-मामेव यदि पूर्वं त्वमेतदर्थमचोदयः । मैथिलीमहमेकाहना तव चानीतवान् भवेः ॥
Rāmāyaṇa, IV. 17.49
37. *Mahāvīracarita* (ed. Ram Chandra Mishra), Benaras, V.S. 2012, p. 228, 234 etc.
38. *Rāmāyaṇa*, IV. 12.39
39. *Asian Variations in Rāmāyaṇa*, op. cit. p. 170.

account. Vālin rather solemnizes Sugrīva's friendship with Rāma, before breathing his last.⁴⁰

While in the epic story, it is Jāmbavān who prompts Hanumān to cross over to Laṅkā to ascertain the whereabouts of Sītā, the task in the play is assigned to him by none else but Rāma himself.⁴¹ Hanumān feels flattered at the assignment and breaks into a boastful account of his might. He could dry up the ocean, build a causeway through it and could transplant there Laṅkā itself, thundered the monkey (*HN*, VI. 4-6). Hanumān's vaunt is not only at variance with the epic version, it is also incompatible with his modesty in answering Rāma's queries, on his return from the mission in Laṅkā. To Rāma's question as to how could he burn down Laṅkā which is supposed to be unassailable, he says with enviable humility that he had been a mere *nimitta* in the exercise. Laṅkā had already been gutted by the fire of your anger and Sītā's burning sigh's.⁴² A monkey, he further adds, has the capacity only to jump from one branch to the other. If he could cross the mighty ocean, his (Rāma's) majesty has doubtless been instrumental in it (*HN*, VI. 44).

The account of war, as given by Dāmodara Miśra, also reveals substantial deviations from its epic prototype. The war in the *HN* begins with Kumbhakarṇa's encounter with the monkey-chief Sugrīva whom he carries away to Laṅkā, though he subsequently manages to return to his camp, after subjecting the demon to quite some harassment (XI. 25). In the duel that follows, Aṅgada releases Sugrīva from the clutches of Kumbhakarṇa, hurling the demon on the ground with his Gāruḍa noose (XI. 31). Nīla sets Kumbhakarṇa

40. *Mahāvīracarita* op. cit. p. 239-40.

41. उत्तिष्ठ हरिशार्दूल लङ्घयस्व महार्णवम् । परा हि सर्वभूतानां हनुमन् या गतिस्तव ॥
Rāmāyaṇa, IV. 66.36

42. निःश्वासेनैव सीतायाः राजन् कोपानलेन ते । दग्धपूर्वा तु सा लंका निमित्तमभवं त्वहम् ॥
HN., VI.43

ablaze (XI. 32). At Rāvaṇa's behest, the clouds send down showers to extinguish the fire (XI. 33).

It is evidently at odd with Vālmīki's version. In the *Rāmāyaṇa* the war begins with Rāvaṇa's duel with Sugrīva (VI. 40), and the monkey turns out to be quite a match to the mighty demon. The outcome of the encounter was indeed flattering for Sugrīva.⁴³ It might have inspired the author of the *HN* to detail his account of Sugrīva's combat with Kumbhakarṇa but it offends the sequence of the story. Whereas Kumbhakarṇa is awakened at Rāvaṇa's instance, even before the first shot is fired,⁴⁴ he is known in the epic version to have been jolted out of slumber at an advanced stage of war, after Rāvaṇa had suffered several reverses and lost some of his doughty warriors.⁴⁵

Kumbhakarṇa's bout with Sugrīva, as described in the epic (VI. 67, 58, 88), is closer to the account in the *HN*, though there is no mention of Aṅgada in the context. The intervening events namely Nīla's setting Kumbhakarṇa on fire to be subsequently quenched by the showers, seem to be peculiar to the play.

The part that Hanumān is assigned to play besides his role, so well known in the epic, also seems to be the innovation of the playwright. He intercepts and throws into the ocean the missile that Rāvaṇa seeks to hurl at Lakṣmaṇa (XIII. 1). It inflames him (Rāvaṇa) beyond measure, and he sets out to kill Brahmā, holding him responsible for the failure of his weapon. Thereupon Brahmā asks his son Nārada to lead Hanumān elsewhere to enable Rāvaṇa to succeed with the weapon. Nārada does accordingly (P. 178, XIII. 2). Rāvaṇa's missile throws into swoon everybody including Lakṣmaṇa; Jāmbavat

43. अथ हरिवरनाथः प्राप्तसंग्रामकीर्तिः। *Rāmāyaṇa*, VI. 40.29.

44. प्रबोध्यतामयं वीरः कुम्भकर्णः। *HN*. p. 159

45. *Rāmāyaṇa*, VI. 60.59

being the only exception.⁴⁶ Rāma curses Māruti for deserting Lakṣmaṇa at the difficult hour (XIII. 11).

Hanumān's chance encounter with Bharata also emerges as a peculiarity of the *HN*. As Hanumān reached Ayodhya in the course of his journey back from the Droṇagiri, to enquire, as bidden by Rāma, of well-being there, Bharata shot him down (XIII.24). He was all but dead. However, on learning of his devotion to Rāma, Vasiṣṭha revived him with the herbs of the mount Droṇa that he had brought with him to cure Lakṣmaṇa of the swoon (XIII. 25-26).

The way Rāvaṇa conducts himself in the play is naggingly inconsistent. With inflated *hauteur* he treats all wise counsel with contempt and goes as far as to boot out his younger brother Vibhīṣaṇa though that turns out to be his undoing. But when reduced to difficult straits in the war, he meekly seeks his wife's advice whether he should release Sītā at that juncture or invite his end at Rāma's hands.⁴⁷ It evokes a sharp retort from her.⁴⁸ He also seems to contemplate a truce with Rāma when he asks him through his envoy Lohitākṣa to surrender to him the axe that he had secured from Paraśurāma (*HN*; P. 195). Which he might have thought, would symbolise his victory over the adversary. Rāma, however, refuses the overtures point blank.⁴⁹ And when locked in the fighting, they slip into an exchange of invectives (XIV. 21-26), Rāma's anguished cry *Bho dīyatām maithilī* (XIV. 29) is also uncharacteristic of him.

Aṅgada too turns out to equally enigmatic, if not more. While he serves Rāma with devotion in all the vicissitudes, on return

46. विभीषणः— जाम्बवन्तमेवापश्यदुपविष्टं मूर्च्छारहितं नान्यम् । *HN*. p. 180.

47. रामाय प्रतिपक्षवृक्षशिखिने दास्यामि वा मैथिली? युद्धे राघवसायकैर्विनिहतः स्वर्गं गमिष्यामि वा? *HN*. XIV. 4.

48. सोऽयं नष्टे कुलेऽस्मिन् कथमिव गमितो जायते ते विवेकः । *HN*. XIV. 5

49. देयो नैष हरप्रसादपरशुः । *HN*. XIV.2.

to Ayodhyā he challenges him to fight so that he may avenge the killing of his father at his hands (XIV. 73). Lakṣmaṇa begs his pardon for his brother's killing the innocent Vālin (XIV. 74). And an ethereal voice assures him that Vālin, destined to be born as a hunter, would himself settle scores with Rāma, when the latter reincarnates as Kṛṣṇa (XIV. 75).

Dāmodara's version ends with the banishment of Sītā for fear of public calumny (XIV. 90), though there is no reference to either her sons or her ultimate departure to the nether region.